

THE EFFECT OF SERVICE COMPENSATION, MOTIVATION, AND DISCIPLINE ON WORK PRODUCTIVITY AND ITS IMPLICATIONS ON SERVICE QUALITY (Study at Malingping Regional Hospital, Banten Province)

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Abstract

Improving the quality of hospital services is greatly influenced by employee productivity. Human resource management factors such as compensation for services, work motivation, and work discipline are crucial elements that can influence productivity and the quality of healthcare services provided to the public. This study aims to analyze the influence of service compensation, motivation, and discipline on work productivity and their implications for service quality at Malingping Regional General Hospital, Banten Province. The study used a quantitative approach with a survey method. Data were collected through questionnaires distributed to 193 hospital employee respondents. Data analysis was performed using path analysis with the help of SPSS version 26. The results of the study indicate that motivation and discipline have a positive and significant effect on employee work productivity, while service compensation does not have a significant partial effect on work productivity. Simultaneously, compensation, motivation, and discipline have a significant effect on work productivity. Furthermore, work productivity has a significant effect on service quality. The coefficient of determination indicates that the variables of compensation, motivation, discipline, and productivity are able to explain 94.1% of the variation in service quality. The results of this study indicate the importance of strengthening employee work motivation and discipline policies to improve the quality of hospital services.

Keywords: *compensation, motivation, work discipline, work productivity, service quality.*

INTRODUCTION

Hospitals are healthcare institutions that play a strategic role in improving public health. Law Number 44 of 2009 concerning Hospitals stipulates that every hospital is required to provide quality, safe, and patient-oriented healthcare services. The quality of healthcare services is greatly influenced by the performance of human resources within the organization. In the context of human resource management, employee productivity is an important factor in determining the quality of services provided to patients. Work productivity is influenced by various factors, including compensation, work motivation, and work discipline. A fair compensation system can improve employee job satisfaction. High work motivation encourages employees to work more optimally, while work discipline creates order in carrying out tasks. This research was conducted at Malingping Regional Hospital, Banten Province, which is a type C regional hospital with a large number of employees and plays an important role in public health services. Based on the current situation, several issues remain related to the service compensation system, work motivation levels, and employee discipline, which can impact work productivity and the quality of hospital services. Therefore, this study aims to analyze the influence of service compensation, motivation, and discipline on work productivity and their implications for service quality.

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LITERATURE REVIEW

Compensation

Compensation encompasses all forms of rewards given to employees in return for their contributions to the organization. A fair compensation system can improve job satisfaction, loyalty, and employee performance within the organization (Rivai & Sagala, 2020). Furthermore, compensation also serves as a human resource management instrument that can influence employee motivation and productivity (Lestari et al., 2023).

Work motivation

Work motivation is an internal drive that influences individual behavior in achieving organizational goals. Robbins and Judge (2020) explain that motivation is a process that explains the intensity, direction, and persistence of individuals in achieving work goals. In the context of modern organizations, motivation is a crucial factor that can improve employee performance and productivity (Luthans, 2021). Recent research also shows that work motivation has a significant influence on improving employee performance in organizations (Esisuarni et al., 2024).

Work Discipline

Work discipline reflects the level of employee compliance with applicable regulations and work standards within the organization. Good discipline can improve work efficiency and minimize operational errors (Sedarmayanti, 2019). In the context of public organizations, work discipline also plays a crucial role in improving employee performance and the quality of public service (Maratus Solikah et al., 2025).

Work Productivity

Work productivity is the ability of employees to produce work output effectively and efficiently by optimally utilizing available resources (Siagian, 2019). In healthcare organizations, the productivity of healthcare workers is a critical factor that can influence the quality of care provided to patients (Wahyuni, 2024).

Quality of Service

Service quality is the level of service excellence perceived by customers. Parasuraman, Zeithaml, and Berry (1988) explain that service quality can be measured through five main dimensions: tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy. In the healthcare sector, improving service quality is a crucial factor in increasing patient satisfaction and public trust in hospitals (Harahap & Siregar, 2022).

METHOD

This study employed a quantitative approach with a survey method. The population was all 373 employees of Malingping Regional Hospital. The sample size was 193 respondents, determined using the Slovin formula. Data were collected using a questionnaire with a five-point Likert scale. Data analysis was performed using path analysis with SPSS 26 software.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Descriptive Analysis

Respondent characteristics in this study included gender, age, education level, and employment status. Based on data processing of 193 respondents, the most dominant respondent characteristics were obtained, as presented in the following table.

Table 1: Respondent Profile and Characteristics Based on Dominant Category

Characteristics	Dominant Category	Number (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Woman	104	53.89%
Age	< 35 Years	90	46.63%
Last education	Professional Bachelor's Degree	125	64.77%
Employee Status	ASN	132	68.39%

Table 1 shows that the study respondents were predominantly female employees (53.89%), with the largest age group under 35 (46.63%). Based on educational level, the majority of respondents had a Bachelor's degree (64.77%), indicating that most employees possess professional qualifications in the health sector. Meanwhile, based on employment status, the respondents were predominantly civil servants (68.39%).

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Table 2 Effect of Variables on Productivity

Independent Variables	Path Coefficient (β)	t count	Significance (Sig)	Information
Service Compensation	-0.063	-0.827	0.409	Not Significant
Work motivation	0.703	14,225	0,000	Significant
Work Discipline	0.231	3,067	0.002	Significant
Coefficient of Determination (R^2)	0.612			

Motivation has the most dominant influence on employee work productivity.

F TEST

Table 3 Model F Calculation Significance (Sig) Description

Model	F Count	Significance (Sig)	Information
Regression Model	94,458	0,000	Significant

A sig. value of $0.000 < 0.05$ indicates that, simultaneously, the variables Compensation, Motivation, and Discipline have a significant influence on Work Productivity. In other words, the regression model you used is appropriate and appropriate for explaining changes in productivity.

Table 4: Results of Analysis of the Influence of Variables on Service Quality

Independent Variables	Beta Coefficient (β)	Significance (Sig)	Information
Compensation	0.060	0.044	Significant
Motivation	0.881	0,000	Very Significant
Discipline	-0.048	0.104	Not Significant
Productivity	0.106	0,000	Very Significant

Motivation Dominance: Just like the previous data, Motivation remains the strongest driving factor (0.881) towards Service Quality.

- a. Work Discipline: In this model, Discipline has a negative direction and a Sig value ($0.104 > 0.05$), which means that statistically it does not have a significant effect on Service Quality in this study.
- b. Compensation & Productivity: Both have a positive and significant influence ($Sig < 0.05$), although their contribution is not as large as Motivation.

Coefficient of Determination

$R^2 = 0.941$

This means that 94.1% of the variation in service quality can be explained by the variables of compensation, motivation, discipline, and work productivity.

Path Analysis Structure Model

The relationship model between variables can be formulated as follows:

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Structural Equation 1

Work Productivity =

$-0.063 \text{ Compensation} + 0.703 \text{ Motivation} + 0.231 \text{ Discipline} + \varepsilon$

Structural Equation 2

Quality of Service =

$0.060 \text{ Compensation} + 0.881 \text{ Motivation} - 0.048 \text{ Discipline} + 0.106 \text{ Productivity} + \varepsilon$

DISCUSSION

The research results show that work motivation has the most dominant influence on employee productivity. Highly motivated employees tend to work more effectively and provide better patient care. This aligns with Robbins and Judge's (2020) findings, which state that motivation is a crucial factor driving individuals to achieve optimal performance. This research finding is also supported by Esisuarni et al.'s (2024) research, which states that work motivation significantly influences employee performance improvement. Work discipline has also been shown to positively impact employee productivity. Adherence to standard operating procedures in healthcare services helps improve work efficiency and minimize service errors. This finding aligns with research by Maratus Solikah et al. (2025), which demonstrated that work discipline significantly impacts employee performance in the public sector.

Meanwhile, compensation for services did not significantly impact work productivity. This suggests that for healthcare workers, professional motivation and commitment to healthcare often outweigh purely financial factors. This study also aligns with research by Putra and Dewi (2022), which found that compensation is not always the primary factor in improving employee performance if employees already possess high intrinsic motivation. The findings of this study also indicate that work productivity significantly impacts the quality of hospital services. Higher employee productivity leads to faster, more accurate, and higher-quality patient care. This aligns with research by Guo et al. (2024), which states that increasing healthcare worker productivity can directly impact the quality of hospital services.

CONCLUSION

- Service compensation does not have a significant effect on employee work productivity.
- Work motivation has a positive and significant effect on work productivity.
- Work discipline has a significant influence on work productivity.
- Simultaneously, compensation, motivation, and discipline have a significant influence on work productivity.
- Work productivity has a significant impact on the quality of hospital services.

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